

TO‘RT O‘LCHAMLI NILPOTENT ALGEBRALARDA LOKAL VA IKKI LOKAL DIFFERENSIALLASH

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Annotatsiya: Bu ishda to‘rt o‘lchovli Nilpotent algebralarda har qanday chiziqli lokal va ikki lokal differensiallashlar differensiallash bo‘lishi isboti bilan ko‘rsatilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Differensiallash, Algebra, lokal differensiallash, chiziqli akslatirish.

Аннотация. В данной работе показано с доказательством, что любые линейные локальные и билочальные дифференциации являются дифференциациями в четырехмерных нильпотентных алгебрах.

Ключевые слова: Дифференциация, алгебра, локальный автоморфизм, линейное отражение.

Abstract. In this work, it is shown with a proof that any linear local and bilocal differentiations are differentiations in four-dimensional Nilpotent algebras.

Key words: Differentiation, Algebra, local differentiation, linear reflection.

Quyida biz to‘rt o‘lchamli nilpotent algebralarning lokal va ikki lokal differensiallashini keltiramiz.

1-Ta‘rif. Agar $d: L \rightarrow L$ chiziqli akslantirish F maydonda berilgan L algebaradan olingan ixtiyoriy x, y elementlar uchun quyidagi shartni qanoatlantirsa

$$d(xy) = d(x)y + xd(y)$$

U holda, akslantirish L algebrada differensiallash deb ataladi.

$d(x) = Ax$ chiziqli akslantirishni qaraylik, buyerde $A - n \times n$ o'lchamli kvadrat matritsa. Ravshanki, agar L algebradan olingan ixtiyoriy x, y elemenlar uchun

$$A(xy) = (Ax)y + x(Ay) \quad (1)$$

tenglik bajarilsa $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish qaralayotgan L algebrada differensiallashdan iborat bo'ladi.

Endi esa lokal differensiallash tushunchasini keltiramiz.

2-Ta'rif. *L algebra bo'lib undagi xar bir $x \in L$ element uchun $\Delta(x) = D_x(x)$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi $D_x: L \rightarrow L$ differensiallash mavjud bo'lsa, u holda $\Delta: L \rightarrow L$ chiziqli akslantirish lokal differensiallash deb ataladi.*

1-Teorema . Ixtiyoriy to'rt o'lchamli nilpotent algebra bazislari $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ bo'lgan quyidagi o'zaro izomorf bo'lmagan algebralarning biriga izomorf bo'ladi:

$$e_1 e_1 = e_2 \quad e_1 e_2 = e_3 \quad e_2 e_1 = e_3$$

Biz bu algebrani differensialini [4] ishda ko'rib o'tganmiz

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{2,1} & 2a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ a_{3,1} & 2a_{2,1} & 3a_{1,1} & a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,1} & 0 & 0 & a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix}$$

Bu yerda quyidagi belgilashni kiritamiz

$$a_{1,1} = \alpha, \quad a_{2,1} = \beta, \quad a_{3,1} = \gamma, \quad a_{4,1} = \delta, \quad a_{3,4} = \varepsilon, \quad a_{4,4} = \epsilon$$

u holda A matritsa bunday ko'rinishga o'tadi.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta & 2\alpha & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma & 2\beta & 3\alpha & \varepsilon \\ \delta & 0 & 0 & \epsilon \end{pmatrix}$$

Quyidagi teoremada A_1 algebra uchun $\Delta: A_1 \rightarrow A_1$ akslantirishni qaraylik.

2-Teorema. A_1 algebraning har qanday chiziqli lokal differensiallashi differensiallashdan iborat.

Isbot. Δ ixtiyoriy local differensiallashi bo'lsin. Barcha $x \in A_1$ uchun ta'rif bo'yicha $\Delta(x) = D_x(x)$ differensiallashi mavjud.

1- teoreмага ko'ra, D_x differensiallashi quyidagi matritsa ko'rinishiga ega:

$$A_x = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_x & 2\alpha_x & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_x & 2\beta_x & 3\alpha_x & \epsilon_x \\ \delta_x & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_x \end{pmatrix}.$$

Xususan $\Delta(e_1) = D_{e_1}e_1, \Delta(e_2) = D_{e_2}e_2, \Delta(e_3) = D_{e_3}e_3, \Delta(e_4) = D_{e_4}e_4$

tengliklarni qanoatlantiruvchi $D_{e_1}, D_{e_2}, D_{e_3}, D_{e_4}$ matritsalar mavjud. A_1 matritsani quyidagicha quraylik:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{e_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_{e_1} & 2\alpha_{e_2} & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_{e_1} & 2\beta_{e_2} & 3\alpha_{e_3} & \epsilon_{e_4} \\ \delta_{e_1} & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{e_4} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Δ chiziqli bo'lgani uchun

$$\Delta(x + y) = \Delta(x) + \Delta(y), \quad \forall x, y \in A_1 \quad (3)$$

tenglik o'rinli.

Bu tenglikka ko'ra

$$\Delta(e_1 + e_2) = \alpha_{e_1+e_2}e_1 + \beta_{e_1+e_2}e_2 + \gamma_{e_1+e_2}e_3 + \delta_{e_1+e_2}e_4 + 2\alpha_{e_1+e_2}e_2 + 2\beta_{e_1+e_2}e_3$$

$$\Delta(e_1) + \Delta(e_2) = \alpha_{e_1}e_1 + \beta_{e_1}e_2 + \gamma_{e_1}e_3 + \delta_{e_1}e_4 + 2\alpha_{e_2}e_2 + 2\beta_{e_2}e_3$$

tengliklarga ega bo'lamiz. Bunda bazis elementlarining koeffitsientlarini taqqoslab, biz quyidagilarga erishamiz:

$$\alpha_{e_1+e_2} = \alpha_{e_1}, \quad \beta_{e_1+e_2} = \beta_{e_1}, \quad \gamma_{e_1+e_2} = \gamma_{e_1}, \quad \delta_{e_1+e_2} = \delta_{e_1},$$

$$\alpha_{e_1+e_2} = \alpha_{e_2}, \quad \beta_{e_1+e_2} = \beta_{e_2}.$$

Bundan esa $\alpha_{e_1} = \alpha_{e_2}, \beta_{e_1} = \beta_{e_2}$ bo'ladi.

$$\text{Endi } \Delta(e_2 + e_3) = 2\alpha_{e_2+e_3}e_2 + 2\beta_{e_2+e_3}e_3 + 3\alpha_{e_2+e_3}e_3$$

$$\Delta(e_2) + \Delta(e_3) = 2\alpha_{e_1}e_2 + 2\beta_{e_1}e_3 + 3\alpha_{e_3}e_3$$

tengliklarga ega bo`lamiz. Bunda bazis elementlarining koeffitsientlarini taqqoslab, biz quyidagilarga erishamiz:

$$\alpha_{e_2+e_3} = \alpha_{e_1}, \quad \beta_{e_1+e_2} = \beta_{e_1}, \quad \alpha_{e_2+e_3} = \alpha_{e_3}$$

Bundan esa $\alpha_{e_1} = \alpha_{e_3}$, bo`ladi.

Shunday qilib, biz Δ lokal differensiallash quyidagi shaklga ega ekanligini bilib olamiz:

$$\Delta = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{e_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_{e_1} & 2\alpha_{e_1} & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_{e_1} & 2\beta_{e_1} & 3\alpha_{e_1} & \epsilon_{e_4} \\ \delta_{e_1} & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{e_4} \end{pmatrix}$$

Teorema isbotlandi.

Endi ikki lokal differensiallashini ko`ramiz

2-Teorema. N_1 algebraning har bir 2-lokal differensiallshi differensialshdir.

Isbot. Aytaylik ∇ – bu N_1 ning ixtiyoriy 2-lokal differensialshlari bo`lsin .

U holda , tarifga ko`ra har bir $x \in N_1$ element uchun ,

$$x = x_1 e_1 + x_2 e_2 + x_3 e_3 + x_4 e_4,$$

$\alpha_{x,e_1}, \beta_{x,e_1}$ shunday elemlar mavjudki

$$A_{x,e_1} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{x,e_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta_{x,e_1} & 2\alpha_{x,e_1} & 0 & 0 \\ \gamma_{x,e_1} & 2\beta_{x,e_1} & 3\alpha_{x,e_1} & \epsilon_{x,e_4} \\ \delta_{x,e_1} & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{x,e_4} \end{pmatrix},$$

$\nabla(x) = A_{x,e_1} \bar{x}$, bu yerda $\bar{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)^T$ – x ga mos vektor va

$$\nabla(e_1) = A_{x,e_1} \bar{e}_1 = (\alpha_{x,e_1}, \beta_{x,e_1}, \gamma_{xe_1}, \delta_{xe_1})^T.$$

Tengliklar $\nabla(e_1) = \varphi_{x,e_1}(e_1) = \nabla_{y,e_1}(e_1)$ o`rinli bo`lgani uchun

$$\nabla(e_1) = (\alpha_{x,e_1}, \beta_{x,e_1}, \gamma_{xe_1}, \delta_{xe_1})^T =$$

$$= (\alpha_{y,e_1}, \beta_{y,e_1}, \gamma_{ye_1}, \delta_{ye_1})^T$$

N_1 dagi elementlarning har bir x, y juftligi uchun .

SHunday kilib ,

$$\alpha_{x,e_1} = \alpha_{y,e_1}, \beta_{x,e_1} = \beta_{y,e_1}, \gamma_{xe_1} = \gamma_{ye_1}, \delta_{xe_1} = \delta_{ye_1})^T$$

Shuning uchun

$$\nabla(x) = A_{y,e_1} \bar{x}$$

Har qanday $x \in N_1$ uchun va $\nabla(x)$ matritsasi x ga bog'liq emas.

SHunday kilib, 1-teoremaga ko'ra , ∇ differensialshdir.

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